

TO INVESTIGATE THE EFFECT OF DIFFERENT MODES OF SALICYLIC ACID ON GROWTH AND YIELD OF CANOLA CULTIVAR UNDER NON-SALINE AND SALINE CONDITIONS

Dr. Zill-E-Huma¹, Muhammad Jawad Umar², Muhammad Ayub³, Muhammad Usman Ghani⁴, Muhammad Bilal Malik⁵, Dr. Abid Ejaz⁶, Dr. Sajid Mahmood^{*7}, Dr. Mian Jahan Zaib Rasheed⁸

^{1,3,6}Department of Botany, University of Sargodha, Sargodha, Pakistan

²Department of Chemistry, Quaid-e-Azam University, Islamabad, Pakistan

⁴Department of Botany, University of Agriculture Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan

⁵Department of Biological Sciences, University of Lahore, Sargodha Campus, Pakistan.

^{*7}Department of Zoology, Hazara University Mansehra, Pakistan

⁸Department of Botany, University of Sargodha, Sargodha, Pakistan

¹humashah690@gmail.com, ²jawadumarsaggu@gmail.com, ³ayubkhansaad@gmail.com, ⁴rana11766@gmail.com, ⁵muhammadbilalmalik8485@gmail.com, ⁶abid155yahoo.com, ^{*7}sajid_sbs12@hu.edu.pk, ⁸jahanzaibrasheedgc@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18324910>

Keywords

Canola, salinity, hoagland's solution, Salicylic acid, biomass production

Article History

Received: 26 November 2025

Accepted: 07 January 2026

Published: 21 January 2026

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Sajid Mahmood

Abstract

A sand culture experiment was conducted in the wire house of old Botanical Garden, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad to study the effect of different modes of salicylic acid on growth and yield of canola cultivar under non-saline and saline conditions. There was only one variety of canola (*Brassica napus* L.) c.v. Hyola-401. Seeds were sown in plastic pots containing 10 kg of thoroughly washed sand and irrigated with half strength of Hoagland's nutrient solution. The experiment was laid out in completely randomized design (CRD) factorial with 3 replications. Two salt levels i.e. 0 and 160 mM L⁻¹ were used to establish salt stress conditions. Three concentrations of salicylic acid (SA) i.e. 0, 0.15 and 0.25 mM L⁻¹ were used through foliar spray and root zone application to minimize the adverse effect of salt stress. After the establishment of treatments, data regarding biomass production was recorded and analyzed statistically. Adverse effect of salt stress on canola plants and ameliorative effect of SA under salt stress was studied in this piece of work.

Introduction

The *Brassica* family has a number of farm crops which are largely grown as cash crops and for industrial purposes. The seed crops of *Brassica* grown for industrial purposes are oil seed rape and mustard. Edible oil is a very important part of our daily routine diet. In Pakistan it was cultivated on

280.6 thousand hectares with an average yield of 837 kg/ha during 2002-2003 (Govt. of Pakistan, 2004).

In current situation, Pakistan is facing a severe shortage of edible oil and only 27.9% the total need is met through local production (Akbar *et al.*, 2007). This wide gap between the production and

consumption is due to the higher population growth rate. This gap is a serious threat to the economy of Pakistan is estimated to increase in next ten years (Katiyar *et al.*, 2000). Canola is very important in bridging this gap between production and consumption due to its high yield potential quality.

Salinity, drought, heat and freezing are environmental conditions that cause adverse effects on the growth of plants (Yamaguchi *et al.*, 2002). Soil salinity is one of the major agro-environmental problems decreasing agricultural productivity on nearly 20% of the cultivated area and half of the irrigated land worldwide (Zhu, 2001) and making more and more land non productive every year (Jaleel *et al.*, 2008). It has been estimated that total salt affected area of the world land is over 800 million hectares. According to an estimate, 397 million hectares of this salt affected land are saline and the remaining 434 million hectares are sodic (FAO, 2005). In Pakistan, the estimated salt affected area is about 6.61 million hectares (Govt. of Pakistan, 2004-2005). Reduction in germination by an increase of salinity levels has been described by numerous authors (El-Tayeb, 2005).

Salinity is most important abiotic stress which increasingly affecting plant health and survival worldwide. Salinity is increasing throughout out the world due to poor local irrigation practices and natural phenomena such as periodic coastal flooding. Therefore, the identification and developing salt tolerant plant using conventional method is of critical importance (Vijayan *et al.*, 2003). Salinity reduces plant growth and crop performance as a result of nutritional disorders. These disorders depend upon nutrient availability, competitive uptake, transport or partitioning within plant. (Molassiotis *et al.*, 2006).

Significant reduction in leaf area, leaf length and root and shoot dry weight is due to high salt level (Ashrafuzzaman *et al.*, 2002). Higher level of

salinity cause reduction in chlorophyll and photosynthetic activity (Hill reaction and CO₂ light fixation (El-Shihaby *et al.*, 2002).

1. To determine which of the different modes of exogenous application of salicylic acid (foliar, seed priming, through root zone application) could be most effective in modulating growth of canola under salt stress.
2. To investigate whether salicylic acid could act as a protectant to ameliorate the influence of salt stress on canola.

Materials and methods

A pot experiment was conducted in the wire house of old Botanical Garden, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad to study the effect of different modes of salicylic acid on growth and yield of canola cultivar under non-saline and saline conditions. There was only one variety of canola (*Brassica napus* L.) c.v. Hyola-401. Seeds were sown in plastic pots containing about 10 kg of sand and irrigated with half strength of Hoagland's nutrient solution. The experiment was laid out in completely randomized design (CRD) factorial with 3 replications.

There were two NaCl treatments

1- 0mM

2- 160mM

Three levels of salicylic acid were used

1- 0mM

2- 0.15mM

3- 0.25mM

Two modes of salicylic acid

1- Foliar spray

2- Root zone application

Salicylic acid (M. Wt. = 138.1) of Sigma Aldrich, Japan was used. Different concentrations of salicylic acid were prepared in distilled water (0, 100, 200 mg/L) in addition 0.1% (v/v) Tweine 20 was added as a surfactant to ensure the penetration of salicylic acid inside the leaf tissue.

Results

Fig.1. Shoot fresh weight of canola plants when grown under non-saline and saline conditions with different modes of salicylic application.

Shoot fresh weight (g)

Analysis of variance of the data for shoot fresh weight of canola cultivar under saline and non-saline conditions with different modes of salicylic (SA) application is presented in Table 1 Fig 1. Salt stress caused a significant reduction in shoot fresh weight of canola (Fig 1). Varying concentrations of SA with different modes of application also show significant effect. Maximum increase in shoot

fresh weight was observed at 0.15 mM SA level when applied through rooting medium under saline conditions. Same was true for non-saline conditions (Fig 1). Slight increase was also observed at 0.15 mM SA level when applied through foliar spray under saline condition. Overall SA application through rooting medium perform better than foliar application.

Fig.2. Root fresh weight of canola plants when grown under non-saline and saline conditions with different modes of salicylic application.

Root fresh weight (g)

The data for root fresh weight of canola cultivar under saline and non-saline conditions with

different modes of salicylic (SA) application is presented in Fig 2. Salt stress caused a significant reduction in root fresh weight of canola (Fig 2).

Different modes of SA application differ considerably for this variable. Maximum increase was observed at 0.15 mM SA level when applied through rooting medium under non-saline conditions (Fig 2). In contrast, marked reduction in root fresh weight was observed at 0.25 mM SA

concentration when applied through rooting medium under saline conditions. Similar reduction was also observed at 0.25 mM SA when applied through foliar spray under non-saline conditions.

Fig.3. Shoot dry weight (g) of canola plants when grown under non-saline and saline conditions with different modes of salicylic application.

Shoot dry weight (g)

The data for shoot dry weight of canola cultivar under saline and non-saline conditions with different modes of salicylic (SA) application is presented in Fig 3. Different modes of SA application differ notably for this variable. Maximum increase was observed at 0.15 mM SA

level when applied through rooting medium or through foliar spray under saline conditions (Fig 3). However these concentrations show an inhibitory effect when applied through foliar spray under non-saline conditions (Fig 3). Over all 0.15 mM SA level was proved to be better under saline conditions.

Fig.4. Root dry weight of canola plants when grown under non-saline and saline conditions with different modes of salicylic application.

Root dry weight (g)

The data for shoot dry weight of canola cultivar under saline and non-saline conditions with different modes of salicylic (SA) application is presented in Fig 4. Different modes of SA application did not differ considerably for this variable. Maximum increase was observed at 0.15 mM SA level when applied through rooting medium or through foliar spray under saline

conditions (Fig 4). However these concentrations show an inhibitory effect when applied through foliar spray under non-saline conditions (Fig 4). Over all 0.15 mM SA level was proved to be better under non-saline and saline conditions when applied through rooting medium. Foliar application caused a reduction in root dry weight of canola cultivar under saline and non-saline conditions (Fig 4).

Fig.5. Number of leaves of canola plants when grown under non-saline and saline conditions with different modes of salicylic application.

Number of leaves

The data for number of leaves of canola cultivar under saline and non-saline conditions with different modes of salicylic (SA) application is presented in Fig 5. Different modes of SA application differ significantly for this variable. Maximum increase was observed at 0.15 mM SA level when applied through rooting medium under saline conditions (Fig 5). However these concentrations show an inhibitory effect when

applied through foliar spray under saline conditions. Whereas 0.25 mM Sa application caused a marked increase in number of leaves when applied through rooting medium under non-saline conditions. Over all 0.15 mM SA level was proved to be better under saline conditions when applied through rooting medium and 0.25 mM SA level was found better when applied through rooting medium under non-saline conditions (Fig 5).

Fig.6. Leaf area (cm²) of canola plants when grown under non-saline and saline conditions with different modes of salicylic application.

Leaf area

The data for leaf area of canola cultivar under saline and non-saline conditions with different modes of salicylic (SA) application is presented in Fig 6. Salt stress caused a significant reduction in leaf area of canola cultivar (Fig 6). Modes of applications of SA also differ significantly under both saline and non-saline conditions. 0.15 mM SA level was found to be more effective to this variable both under saline and non-saline

conditions when applied through rooting medium (Fig 6). In contrast higher concentration i.e. 0.25 mM SA level caused an inhibitory effect when applied through rooting medium under saline conditions. However varying concentrations of SA through foliar spray was remained ineffective under saline conditions whereas it showed reduction in leaf area under non-saline conditions (Fig 6).

Fig.7. Shoot length (cm) of canola plants when grown under non-saline and saline conditions with different modes of salicylic application.

Shoot length (cm)

The data for shoot length of canola cultivar under saline and non-saline conditions with different modes of salicylic (SA) application is presented in Fig 7. Maximum increase was observed at 0.15 mM SA level when applied through rooting medium or through foliar spray under saline conditions (Fig 7). Same was true in case of foliar

application under non-saline conditions, while 0.25 mM SA level show a marked increase in shoot length of canola cultivar when applied through rooting medium under non-saline conditions. Overall SA application through rooting medium was found to be better as compare to foliar application.

Fig.8. Root length (cm) of canola plants when grown under non-saline and saline conditions with different modes of salicylic application.

Root length (cm)

Root length of canola cultivar under saline and non-saline conditions with different modes of salicylic (SA) application is presented in Fig 8. Salt stress caused a noteworthy reduction in root length of canola (Fig 8). Maximum increase was

observed at 0.25 mM SA level when applied through foliar spray under non-saline conditions (Fig 8). However under saline conditions, a decreasing trend was observed when SA was applied through rootin medium or through foliar spray.

Fig.9. Total leaf area of canola plants when grown under non-saline and saline conditions with different modes of salicylic application.

Total leaf area per plant

Data for total leaf area per plant of canola cultivar under saline and non-saline conditions with different modes of salicylic (SA) application is presented in Fig 9. Salt stress caused a considerable reduction in total leaf area per plant of canola cultivar (Fig 9). Modes of applications of SA also differ significantly under both saline and non-saline conditions. 0.15 mM SA level was found to be more effective to this variable both

under saline and non-saline conditions when applied through rooting medium (Fig 9). In contrast higher concentration i.e. 0.25 mM SA level caused an inhibitory effect when applied through rooting medium under saline conditions. However varying concentrations of SA through foliar spray was remained ineffective under saline conditions whereas it showed reduction in total leaf area per plant under non-saline conditions (Fig 9).

Fig.10. Plant height (cm) of canola plants when grown under non-saline and saline conditions with different modes of salicylic application.

Plant height (cm)

Salt stress caused a significant reduction in plant height of canola cultivar (Fig 10). Modes of SA application did not differ under saline and non-saline conditions. However SA applied via rooting medium show a marked increase in plant height under saline conditions, whereas SA application through foliar spray did not show any increasing

or decreasing effect under saline conditions (Fig 10). Under non saline conditions, 0.15 and 0.25 mM SA levels show increase in plant height when applied both through rooting medium and through foliar spray. Overall SA applied through rooting medium was found to be better as compare to foliar application both under saline and non-saline conditions.

Fig.11. Number of pods of canola plants when grown under non-saline and saline conditions with different modes of salicylic application.

Number of pods

Analysis of variance of the data for number of pods of canola cultivar under saline and non-saline conditions with different modes of salicylic (SA) application is presented in (Fig 11). Salt stress caused a considerable reduction in number of pods of canola cultivar (Fig 11). Modes of applications of SA also differ significantly under both saline and non-saline conditions. However, maximum reduction in number of pods was

observed in at 0.15 and 0.25 mM SA level when applied through foliar spray under saline conditions and under non-saline conditions, there is no increasing or decreasing effect to this variable at 0.15 and 0.25 mM SA level when applied through foliar spray. However, a slight increase was observed at 0.15 mM SA when applied through rooting medium under non-saline conditions (Fig 11).

Fig.12. Total seed weight per plant of canola plants when grown under non-saline and saline conditions with different modes of salicylic application.

Total seed weight

Analysis of variance of the data for total seed weight of canola cultivar under saline and non-saline conditions with different modes of salicylic (SA) application is presented in (Fig 12). Salt stress caused reduction in total seed weight (Fig 12). Modes of applications of SA differ significantly under both saline and non-saline conditions. However, a slight increase in total seed weight was observed at 0.15 and mM SA when applied through foliar spray under saline conditions (Fig 12). Same was true for non-saline conditions when 0.15 mM SA was applied through rooting medium under non-saline conditions (Fig 12).

Discussions

In view of the results obtained from this experiment, it is evident that salt stress caused a reduction in growth and yield of canola cultivar. However, this adverse effect of salt stress was prominent on photosynthesizing leaves, plant dry biomass, number of pods and total seed weight. (Iqbal and Ashraf, 2005; Faroudi and Sharifzadeh, 2006). SA application through rooting medium exacerbated the adverse effects of salt stress on the vegetative growth of canola cultivar, whereas it significantly increased plant fresh biomass and number of pods. Thus, it is possible that SA application caused a diversion of assimilates from vegetative parts to pods and seeds.

The distribution of photoassimilates among sinks (vegetative and reproductive organs) is primarily regulated by sinks themselves (Ho et al., 1989; Marcelis, 1996). The developing grains of canola cultivars seemed to be strong sinks for assimilates demand for their growth and development, so they might have reduced the partitioning of assimilates to the vegetative organs. Cockshull (1982) stated that the terminal inflorescence buds of *Chrysanthemum morifolium* were act as strong sinks for photoassimilates and removal of the terminal buds increased the diversion of assimilates to the vegetative organs, particularly to the leaves.

In the present study, the most effective concentration of SA in decreasing growth and increasing seed weight was 0.15 mM L⁻¹ when applied through rooting medium. Although SA

application through rooting medium or foliar spray with SA caused an increase in yield of different crops, e.g., rice (Jayachandran et al., 2001), mulberry (Singhvi et al., 2002), and pearl millet (Sivakumar et al., 2001), the effective concentration of SA for yield improvement was different. For example, the most effective concentration of SA was 150 mg L⁻¹ for rice, 100 mg L⁻¹ for tomato and pearl millet, and 125 mg L⁻¹ for mulberry. From these findings as well as those reported here, it can be suggested that the effective concentration of SA in increasing yield was species or cultivar specific.

In the present study, SA application through rooting medium was more effective in alleviating the adverse effects of salt stress on vegetative growth and yield when applied through rooting medium. This differential response of SA application in alleviating the adverse effects of salt stress on fresh biomass and number of pods can be expected, because plants which were treated with SA through rooting medium had been subjected to salt stress for longer period without those which were treated with SA through foliar spray. This factor may have played a vital role in the differential response of canola cultivar to SA application through different modes of application.

REFERENCES

- Akbar, M., tahira and M. Hussain. 2007. Heterosis for seed yield and its components in Rapeseed. J. Agric. Res., 45: 95-104.
- Cockshull, K. E. 1982. Disbudding and its effect on dry matter distribution in *Chrysanthemum morifolium*. J. Hort. Sci. 57: 205-207.
- El-Tayeb, M.A. 2005. Response of barely grains to the interactive effect of salinity and salicylic acid. Plant Growth Regul., 45: 215-224.
- FAO. 2005. Global network on integrated soil management for sustainable Use of salt affected soils. Rome. Italy. FAO Land and Plant Nutrition Management for service.

- Faroudi, R. and Sharifzadeh. 2006. The effect of NaCl priming on salt tolerance in canola seedlings grown under saline conditions. *Indian J. Crop. Sci.*, 1: 74-78.
- Ho, L. C., Grange, R. I., and Shaw, A. F. 1989. Source/sink regulation. In: Baker, D.A., Milburn, J. (Eds.), *Transport of Photoassimilate*. Long man, London, pp. 306-343.
- Jaleel. C. A., B. Sankar, R, Sridharan and R. Paneerselvam. 2008. Soil salinity alters growth chlorophyll content and secondary metabolite accumulation in *Catharanthus roseus*. *Truk. J. Biol.*, 32: 79-83.
- Jayachandran, M., Rajendran, P. and Thangaraj, M. 2001. Effect of growth regulators on growth and yield of wet season rice. *Madras Agric. J.*, 87: 340-342.
- Katiyar, R. K., R. Chamola and V. L. Chopra. 2000. Heterosis and combining ability in Indian mustard [*brassica juncea* (L.) Czern and Cross]. *Indian J. Genet. Pi. Br.*, 60: 557-559.
- Marcelis, L. F. M. 1996. Sink strength as a determinant of dry matter partitioning in the whole plant. *J. Exp. Bot.* 47:1281-1297.
- Molassiotis, A.N., Sotiropoulos, S., Tanou, G., Kofidis, G., Diamantidis, G., Therios, I., 2006, Antioxidant and anatomical responses in shoot culture of the apple rootstock MM 106 treated with NaCl, KCl, mannitol or sorbitol, *Biol. Plant.*, 50 (1): 61-68.
- Singhvi, N. R., Kodandaramaiah, J., Rekha, M., Sarkar, A. and Datta, R. K. 2002. Influence of salicylic acid on mulberry growth and leaf yield. *Avances in Plnat Sci.*, 15: 463-466.
- Sivakumar, R., Kalarani, M. K., Mallika, V. and Sujatha, K. B. 2001. Effect of growth regulators on biochemical attributes, grain yield and quality in pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum* L.R. Br.). *Madras Agric. J.*, 88: 256- 259.
- Vijayan K, Chakraborti SP, Ghosh PD (2003). In vitro screening of mulberry (*Morus* spp.) for salinity tolerance. *Plant Cell Rep.*, 22: 350- 357.
- Yamaguchi S. K., M. kasuga, Q. Liu, Nakashima, Y. Sakuma and Y. Habe. 2002. Biological mechanism of drought stress response. *JIRCAS Working Report*, pp:1-8.
- Zhu, J. K., 2001. Plant salt tolerance. *Trends Plant Sci.*, 6: 66-71.